

MECHANICAL BEHAVIOUR OF NON-CRIMP 3D WOVEN CARBON/EPOXY COMPOSITE UNDER IN-PLANE TENSILE LOADING

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1 Introduction

The principal trend in aerospace industry is to develop “Out-of-Autoclave” technologies that would enable same level of composites’ properties as conventional prepreg tape laminates but at significantly reduced manufacturing cost and time. As described in [1], a relatively new class of unitary (single-ply) composites reinforced with non-crimp 3D orthogonal woven (NC3DOW) preforms, produced on the specialty 3D weaving machines, does not possess any macro-interfaces and is characteristic with practically straight and well aligned in-plane fibers. As a consequence, this type of textile composites shows significantly higher in-plane elastic moduli and even higher in-plane strengths than composites reinforced with more conventional 3D interlock weaves usually produced on traditional 2-D weaving machines.

The non-crimp 3D orthogonal weaving process and machines developed at North Carolina State University in the early 1990s [1] are currently used by 3TEX, Inc. in commercial manufacturing of non-crimp 3D orthogonal woven fabrics under trademark 3WEAVE[®]. The specialty 3-D orthogonal weaving machines designed and built by 3TEX ensure high consistency of the preform architecture and minimal waviness of the in-plane (warp- and fill-directional) fibers. Also importantly, it was shown in several recent experimental studies (most detailed of them can be found in [2-8]), there is very low general waviness of all of the warp- and fill-directional yarns which allows to achieve somewhat higher in-plane elastic moduli and even higher in-plane strengths and damage initiation characteristics of the

studied 3WEAVE[®] composites in comparison with their 2D woven laminated counterparts.

The paper presents the most important results of internal fiber architecture, elastic and strength properties, as well as damage progression in the cases of in-plane quasi-static and fatigue tensile loading of one specific NC3DOW carbon fiber/epoxy composite.

2 Materials

NC3DOW preform (Fig.1a) was produced by 3TEX, Inc. on one of their proprietary 3D weaving machines. The fabric unit cell consists of three warp and four fill yarn layers with the yarn insertion density 4.72 ends/cm, 3.91 picks/cm and Z yarn 1/end. All warp layers use 12K Toho Tenax HTS40 F13 carbon yarn; all fill layers use 6K Toho Tenax HTS40 E13 (which is doubled in weaving by the cyclic rapier motion); Z yarns are 1K Toho Tenax HTA40 H15. Fiber weight ratio is 46.1% warp/ 51.2% fill / 2.6% Z. Flat panels were fabricated by 3TEX using VARTM with epoxy resin West System 105 and 209 Extra Slow Hardener.

The internal fiber architecture of NC3DOW (Fig.1b,c) studied in [5] demonstrate high straightness of the in-plane yarns and high uniformity of the geometry. The measured waviness values for the yarns belonging to all warp and fill layers are below 0.1%. As expected, they reach their largest values for the fill yarns in the first and fourth layers, where the waviness caused by Z-crowns is dominating. For these yarns, the waviness is even visible in their shapes. But even for these yarns the measured waviness is below 0.1%. For the fill yarns in the inner (second and third) layers, as well as for

all three warp yarn layers, the waviness values are below 0.05%. The variability of dimensions of the yarns is in the range of 4-8% for warp and fill directions; the yarn spacing varies in the range of 3-4%. These low values show cardinaly improved fiber straightness and uniformity over respective geometry characteristics typically observed on 2D woven, angle interlock 3D woven and structurally stitched 3D composites. The fiber volume fractions inside the yarns were found to be in the range of 61...70% for warp and 64...73% for fill directions.

Fig. 1 Internal geometry of the non-crimp 3D orthogonal woven composite: (a) weave; (b) microCT slices parallel to the warp direction (the specimen after fatigue loading) (images: G. Kerckhofs)

2. Elastic and strength properties

Stress-strain curves, Young's moduli, Poisson's ratios, ultimate stresses and strains have been

experimentally determined in [6]. A considerable gradual growth of the Young's moduli under loading in warp and fill directions was revealed for strains from 0.1% to ~0.9% (Fig.2). The growth is followed by a slow gradual reduction of the moduli with further increase of strain. The "non-Hookean" behavior is attributed to a combination of carbon fiber stiffening and fiber straightening, the latter appears to be a minor cause contributing not more than 20% into the modulus vs. strain variations. Theoretical predictions using Orientational Averaging Method showed excellent agreement with experimental data for in-plane elastic moduli - after the adjustment of theoretical predictions for the fiber waviness and the fiber stiffening effects, the predicted Young's moduli exceeded the respective experimental values (e.g., warp-directional modulus 60.1 GPa and fill-directional modulus 64.3 GPa) by only 1.6% in warp and 0.3% in fill directions.

The warp-directional tensile strength was found to be 953 MPa and fill-directional strength 901 MPa; the former one is 5.8% larger contrary to a 5.1% higher fiber weight fraction in fill direction. This effect can be mainly attributed to the difference in fiber damage/fracture amount imparted during weaving and local irregularities of the surface fill yarn geometry owed to their interaction with Z-crowns, see Fig. 1a; as seen in the figure, no warp yarns are located on the fabric surface to interact in the same fashion with Z-crowns).

3. Progressive damage during quasi-static tension

The methodology described in [9] which combines acoustic emission, strain-mapping, and X-ray damage imaging was used in [7] to conduct a thorough investigation of the damage mechanisms in the composite under consideration.

Firstly, a delayed damage initiation has been observed. The damage initiation for the loading in warp or fill directions occurs in the range of applied strain 0.4...0.6% (Fig.2, showing the data for fill-direction loading). This is significantly higher than the range of damage initiation strains (0.2...0.4%) obtained for the earlier studied E-glass/epoxy-vinyl ester composites reinforced with the same type NC3DOW fabrics [2,3]. This range of damage initiation strains is also significantly higher than the respective ranges observed for other carbon/epoxy textile composites, and is at the lower end of the

typical damage initiation strain range (0.6...0.7%) for conventional cross-ply prepreg tape laminates (see details of respective comparisons in [7]).

Fig.3 presents the micrographs of cross sections of the composite on the various stages of the loading, as indicated in Fig. 2. Different types of the cracks are shown in Table 1.

Fig. 2 Stress-strain diagrams and acoustic emission. Representative fill- directional test, dependency on the applied strain of: stress (σ), Young modulus (E), energy of individual AE events and cumulative energy (arbitrary units). ϵ_{min} , ϵ_1 , ϵ_2 : damage thresholds. Micrographs were made on samples loaded up to strain A, B and U

Fig. 3 Micrographs of damage. Loading in fill direction. Load levels (see Figure 7): A (a-c), B (d-f),U (g-i). (a) no cracks; (b-i) cracks indicated by arrows, the labels designate the crack type: “b”, “t”, “l” and “m” (explanation of this terminology is in the text)

The damage in the studied composite starts near the location of Z-yarns as local disbands, which are formed at the edges of the in-plane yarns oriented transversely to the loading direction. Transversal cracks inside the in-plane yarns do develop later in the loading process; those, in turn, are followed by the local disbands parallel to the surface of the composite at a very late stage of loading.

Table 1 Types of the cracks, observed in cross sections and X-ray images

Description	Notation	Direction
Cracks on the boundary of the yarns	b	Normal to the sample surface and to the loading direction
Transverse matrix cracks inside the yarns	t	Normal to the sample surface and to the loading direction
Debondings on the surface of the yarns and local delaminations inside the yarns	l	Parallel to the sample surface and to the loading direction
Cracks on the boundary of Z-yarns	Z	Follow the surface of Z-yarns
Transverse cracks in the matrix pockets	mt	Normal to the sample surface and to the loading direction
Longitudinal cracks in the matrix pockets	ml	Parallel to the sample surface and to the loading direction

Significant difference in the distribution of AE event energy for the loading in the warp and fill directions has been observed. More of the higher energy events and continuous AE energy spectrum for the fill-directional loading can be attributed to the presence of (although very low) undulations of the fill yarns in the surface layers. Those features are also associated with the higher amount of transverse cracks and local disbands in the later stages of the material loading in fill direction.

Comparison of the damage behavior between the angle interlock 3D woven composites [10,11] and the presently studied NC3DOW composite shows that the latter does not exhibit as high strain-to-failure values at which the primary load-bearing tows have failed in the former ones. However, owed to the non-Hookean behavior of practically straight carbon fibers in the present composite and to the high degree of realization of the load-carrying capability of fibers, the present NC3DOW composite shows the energy absorption capability comparable to the one observed for the angle interlock 3D weave carbon/epoxy composites.

5. Tension-tension fatigue

Tension-tension fatigue of NC3DOW carbon/epoxy composite was studied in [8]). A hydraulic Schenk

testing machine was used for the fatigue tests, which were performed under constant maximum stress, sinusoidal wave-form tensile-tensile loading with 6 Hz frequency and the ratio $R = 0.1$ (ratio of the minimum to the maximum stress in the cycle).

Fatigue life curve (Fig. 4) is well represented by a tri-linear diagram. The critical level of maximum stress, corresponding to 3,000,000 cycles, has been assessed as at least 412 MPa for both warp- and fill-directional loading cases. This value is almost two times higher than the damage initiation threshold obtained in the quasi-static tests of the same material and is close to the second damage threshold, corresponding to the onset of local disbond cracks parallel to the sample facings.

The post-fatigue state of damage was studied using X-ray examination and optical microscopy of cross sections of one of the specimens of each group in tension in order to study two post-fatigue effects: (i) the change of Young's modulus and strength as a result of the fatigue loading, and (ii) the change of the damage progression in samples loaded up to failure after fatigue; in both cases a comparison with the non-fatigued material samples has been performed. The decrease of the composite modulus during fatigue loading does not exceed 5%. The initial Young's modulus values obtained from the post-fatigue tensile tests are close to the maximum values obtained in the quasi-static tensile testing. Post-fatigue quasi-static strength of the composite showed 11...12% lower than that of the composite not exposed to a prior fatigue loading.

The observed damage development in an early stage is characterized by a combination of transversal cracks in the fiber bundles, boundary disbond cracks at the surfaces of fiber bundles transversal to the loading direction, and local disbond cracks parallel to the sample facings. This crack system pattern, developing during fatigue loading, is repeating in each and every unit cell of the composite. The next damage development stage includes the length increase of the cracks and their opening, followed by the formation of splitting cracks among individual fibers; the latter damage development is viewed as a predecessor of the ultimate failure of this type composite under fatigue loading.

Fig 4 Tension-tension fatigue S-N curves of NC3DOW carbon/epoxy composite

The S-N curves obtained for the present NC3DOW carbon/epoxy composite were compared with the results of The Versailles Project on Advanced Materials and Standards (VAMAS) for unidirectional carbon/epoxy composites [12] and with the previously reported results for structurally stitched and unstitched NCF composites [13]. The stress levels for different cases were normalized over respective static tensile strengths. The tests reported in [12,13] were performed for tension-tension cyclic loading with the same value of $R = 0.1$ and the same frequency range as used in the present work. Carbon fibers used in [13] were same grade Toho Tenax HTS used for the composite studied here. The data show that the fatigue life of NC3DOW carbon/epoxy composite is close to the fatigue life of structurally stitched NCF carbon/epoxy composites for identical normalized maximum stress values.

6. Conclusions

The results of detailed analysis of the internal architecture and mechanical behaviour of a NC3DOW carbon/epoxy composite has been reported. The study has confirmed the paramount importance of the absence of warp and fill yarn crimp and waviness in this class of 3D woven composites for achieving their advantageous mechanical properties. The following results are the most important:

- Cardinaly improved fiber straightness and yarn placement uniformity over respective geometry characteristics typically observed on 2D woven, angle interlock 3D woven and structurally stitched 3D composites.

- A linearity of the stress-strain response up to failure, even after the onset of damage in the yarns transverse to the loading direction. A considerable non-Hookean effect in the stress-strain curves has been observed and explained by the intrinsic stiffening of the carbon fibers.
- A delayed damage initiation has been observed, with the damage threshold significantly higher than respective values observed earlier for other carbon/epoxy textile composites. The obtained damage threshold is at the lower end of the typical damage initiation strain range (0.6...0.7%) for conventional cross-ply prepreg tape laminates.
- The energy absorption capability is comparable to the one obtained earlier for the angle interlock 3D weave carbon/epoxy composites.
- The critical level of maximum stress, corresponding to 3,000,000 cycles, is at least 412 MPa for both warp- and fill-directional loading cases. This value is almost two times higher than the damage initiation threshold obtained in the quasi-static tests of the same material.

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